

HOW TEACHERS AND STUDENTS CAN PARTICIPATE IN THE DECADE OF ACTION FOR CRYOSPHERIC SCIENCES 2025 – 2034

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The implementation of the Decade of Action for Cryospheric Sciences 2025–2034 [1] aims to involve pupils and students of Ukraine in realizing the importance of changes in the climate system and the hydrological cycle, their impact on the sustainable development of the economy, society and nature of the Earth.

Are there any questions that are of great interest to students? Yes, there are, and they are always surprised when they learn that about 270 thousand years ago, the tongue of the ancient glacier reached the modern city of Kamianske, Dnipropetrovsk region. Then they begin to ask the question of how, when, and why ancient glaciations were formed and what changes occurred in nature during the geological history of the Earth. With these questions, the search and research activities of students can begin.

Despite the significant amount of research results on this issue in general secondary education institutions, teachers and students do not have thorough methodological developments in glaciological research or forms of active participation in the Decade of Action for Cryospheric Sciences 2025 – 2034. We hope that specialists will respond during the decade to the solution of this methodological problem with their lengthy comments. What can be done today? study of the Little Ice Age of the XV – XIX centuries. We see as interdisciplinary project research: (a) geographical research* – the study of geological activity in different periods; hydrological research* – periods of sharp warming of the ocean, and then its cooling in 1380 – 1400; glaciological research* – melting of mountain and cover glaciers; (b) astronomical research – the study of anomalous periods of solar activity; (c) historical research – popular uprisings, persecution of "witches", changes in human settlement patterns have become more frequent; (d) economic research – crop failures due to extreme weather conditions and locust infestations, construction of anti-virus infrastructure; (e) sociological studies – mass famine, pandemics, deaths of millions of people in Europe, migration of the population to more favorable areas, etc.

For example, studying the history of the solar cycle from 1750 to 2025 on the NOAA/SWPC website [2]. Apply an activity approach in teaching geography to better understand the rhythmic processes in the Earth's geographical envelope. Of course, in order to adequately present the results of student research projects, it is necessary to organize student scientific conferences on glaciological processes. Writing research papers in the system of the Junior Academy of Sciences of Ukraine (JAS of Ukraine) can serve as a continuation, probably this will affect their choice of future profession.

Significant assistance in educational activities for Ukrainian students and teachers is provided by researchers of the State Institution National Antarctic Scientific Center of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine. These are a variety of educational materials about the uniqueness of the nature of Antarctica, research at the Akademik Vernadsky station, and well-known Antarctic video lessons with Yevhen Dykyi, Anzhelika Gapchuk, Maria Pavlovska, and others [3].

What about practical work on the ground? The modern school has such examples, but they are not widely disseminated. It may relate to the study of landforms (geomorphological studies*) that were formed from ancient or modern forms of glaciation. In Ukraine, they are also widely represented, for example, – accumulative water-glacial forms (lakes, cones of drift), exarchate valleys, and moraine covers in Volyn, Poltava, Kyiv, Kirovohrad, Transcarpathian, and other regions of the country.

* Geological, lithological, glaciological, hydrological, geomorphological foundations of sciences in the educational system of Ukraine do not have separate academic subjects and therefore we refer them to the objects of geography research.

1. Decade of Action for Cryospheric Sciences, 2025-2034 : resolution / adopted by the General Assembly (A/RES/78/321) on 14 August 2024]. URL.:

<https://digitallibrary.un.org/record/4060788?v=pdf> (last accessed 2025/01/13).

2. Space Weather Prediction Center. National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration USA. URL. : <https://www.spaceweather.gov/products/solar-cycle-progression> (last accessed 2025/02/16).

3. State Institution National Antarctic Science Center. Educational materials. URL. : <http://uac.gov.ua/educational-material/> (last accessed 2025/02/16).